

Exact Inference for Quantum Circuits: A Testing Oracle for Quantum Software Stacks (Companion Report)

Postulate 1 (Observables and States) The quantum mechanical expectation value of an observable A in a mixed state ρ is given by $\langle A \rangle_\rho := \text{tr}(\rho A)$.

Postulate 2 (Measurement Probability) If the quantum system is in a state ρ , λ is an eigenvalue of A and P_λ the projection onto the eigenspace of λ , then the probability $P_\rho(\lambda)$ that a measurement of A yields the value λ is given by $P_\rho(\lambda) = \text{tr}(\rho P_\lambda)$.

Postulate 3 (Projection Postulate) If the quantum system is initially described by the state ρ , and then the measurement of the observable A yields the eigenvalue λ of A , then this measurement has effected the following change of state

$$\rho = \text{state before measurement} \xrightarrow{\text{measurement}} \frac{P_\lambda \rho P_\lambda}{\text{tr}(\rho P_\lambda)} = \text{state after measurement}$$

where P_λ is the projection onto the eigenspace of λ .

Postulate 4 (Time Evolution) Any time evolution of a quantum system that is not caused by a measurement is described as an evolution of states

$$\rho(t_0) = \text{state at time } t_0 \xrightarrow{\text{no measurement}} \rho(t) = \text{state at time } t$$

given by a unitary time evolution operator $U(t, t_0)$ acting on the density operator as $\rho(t) = U(t, t_0)\rho(t_0)U(t, t_0)^*$.

Postulate 5 (Mixed States) In general a quantum mechanical system is described mathematically by an operator ρ acting on a HILBERT space \mathbb{H} with ρ having the properties:

- ρ is self-adjoint: $\rho^* = \rho$.
- ρ is positive semi-definite: $\rho \geq 0$.
- ρ has trace 1: $\text{tr}(\rho) = 1$.

The operator ρ is called density operator and we denote the set of density operators on a HILBERT space \mathbb{H} by $D(\mathbb{H})$, that is, $D(\mathbb{H}) := \{\rho \in L(\mathbb{H}) \mid \rho^* = \rho, \rho \geq 0, \text{tr}(\rho) = 1\}$. The quantum states described by density operators in $D(\mathbb{H})$ are called mixed states.

Figure 1: The exact quote of the postulates of quantum computing summarized by Scherer [?]

Postulate 1 (Gate). *The change of a density matrix from ρ to ρ' by a gate is described by $\rho' = M\rho M^*$ where M is a unitary matrix, i.e., $M^*M = I$.*

Theorem 2 (Rotation Gate). *Suppose that the following holds: $(\rho, \sigma, P) \vdash \text{U}(r_1, r_2, r_3) \ q \Rightarrow (\rho', \sigma', P')$. Then, there exists a unitary matrix M such that $\rho' = M\rho M^*$.*

Proof. By rule [EVAL-ROTATE], $\rho' = M\rho M^*$ where $M = U_{\text{qbts}(\rho), q, r_1, r_2, r_3}$. Therefore, it is enough to show that M is unitary. We can easily show that a 2×2 matrix U_{r_1, r_2, r_3} and the identity matrix of any dimension are unitary. Since the tensor product of unitary matrices is also unitary, M is unitary. \square

Theorem 3 (Cnot Gate). *Suppose that the following holds: $(\rho, \sigma, P) \vdash \text{CX } q_1 \ q_2 \Rightarrow (\rho', \sigma', P')$. Then, there exists a unitary matrix M such that $\rho' = M\rho M^*$.*

Proof. By rule [EVAL-CNOT], $\rho' = M\rho M^*$ where $M = \text{CX}_{qbts(\rho), q_1, q_2}$, it is enough to show that M is unitary. We prove it by induction on $n = qbts(\rho)$. When $n = 1$, $M = I_1$ is unitary. We now focus on the case where $n > 1$.

- $q_1 = 0 \wedge q_2 = 0$. $M = I_n$ is unitary.
- $q_1 = 0 \wedge q_2 > 0$. From $M = \text{Proj}_0 \otimes I_{n-1} + \text{Proj}_1 \otimes X_{n-1, q_2-1}$, we can easily show $M^*M = I_n$.
- $q_1 > 0 \wedge q_2 = 0$. Similar to the second case.
- $q_1 > 0 \wedge q_2 > 0$. $M = I_1 \otimes \text{CX}_{n-1, q_1-1, q_2-1}$, where $\text{CX}_{n-1, q_1-1, q_2-1}$ is unitary by induction hypothesis. Therefore, $M^*M = (I_1^* I_1) \otimes (\text{CX}_{n-1, q_1-1, q_2-1}^* \text{CX}_{n-1, q_1-1, q_2-1}) = I_n$.

□

Postulate 4 (Measurement). *For a quantum system described by a density matrix ρ , a physical observable to be measured is represented by a self-adjoint matrix A , whose dimension is the same as ρ . Each measurement outcome corresponds to λ , an eigenvalue of A . The probability of the outcome corresponding to λ is $\text{tr}(\rho M)$ where M is the projection onto the eigenspace of λ . The change of a density matrix from ρ to ρ' by the measurement is described by $\rho' = \frac{1}{\text{tr}(\rho M)} M\rho M$.*

Theorem 5 (Measurement). *Suppose that the following holds: $(\rho, \sigma, P) \vdash c := \text{Measure } q \Rightarrow \overline{\Sigma'}$. Then, $\exists A. \forall \Sigma' \in \{\overline{\Sigma'}\}. \exists \lambda$ such that the followings hold: (1) A is self-adjoint; (2) λ is an eigenvalue of A ; (3) M is the projection operator onto the eigenspace of λ ; (4) $w' = (\rho', \sigma', P')$; (5) $\rho' = \frac{1}{\text{tr}(\rho M)} M\rho M$; (6) $\frac{P'}{P} = \text{tr}(\rho M)$.*

Proof. By [EVAL-MEAS], [EVAL-MEAS-0], and [EVAL-MEAS-1], $\Sigma' \in \{\overline{\Sigma'}\}$ is either $(msr(\rho, \text{Proj}_{n,q,0}), \sigma[c \mapsto 0], P \times \text{prob}(\rho, \text{Proj}_{n,q,0}))$ or $(msr(\rho, \text{Proj}_{n,q,1}), \sigma[c \mapsto 1], P \times \text{prob}(\rho, \text{Proj}_{n,q,1}))$ where $n = qbts(\rho)$. Let $A = I_q \otimes \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \otimes I_{n-q-1}$. We can easily show that 1 and -1 are eigenvalues of A , and $\text{Proj}_{n,q,0}$ and $\text{Proj}_{n,q,1}$ are their corresponding projections. □

Postulate 6 (Density Matrix). *A density matrix ρ satisfies the following: (1) ρ is self-adjoint: $\rho^* = \rho$; (2) ρ is positive semi-definite: $\rho \geq 0$, i.e., $z^* \rho z \geq 0$ for every column vector z ; (3) $\text{tr}(\rho) = 1$.*

Theorem 7 (Density Matrix). *Suppose that the following holds: $(\rho, \sigma, P) \vdash s \Rightarrow \overline{\Sigma'}$. If ρ is self-adjoint and positive semi-definite and $\text{tr}(\rho) = 1$, then for every $(\rho', \sigma', P') \in \{\overline{\Sigma'}\}$, ρ' is self-adjoint and positive semi-definite and $\text{tr}(\rho') = 1$.*

Proof. We prove it by structural induction on s .

- $s = \text{nop}$. By rule [EVAL-NOP], $\rho' = \rho$.
- $s = s_1; s_2$. We prove it using rule [EVAL-SEQ] and the induction hypothesis.
- $s = \text{if } c \rightsquigarrow b \text{ then } s'$. If $\sigma(c) \neq b$, $\rho' = \rho$ by rule [EVAL-IF-FALSE]. If $\sigma(c) = b$, we prove it using rule [EVAL-IF-TRUE] and the induction hypothesis.
- $s = \text{U}(r_1, r_2, r_3) \ q$ or $s = \text{CX } q_1 \ q_2$. By Theorems 2 and 3, $\rho' = M\rho M^*$ where M is unitary. Basic linear algebra allows us to prove it using that M is unitary.
- $s = c := \text{Measure } q$. By Theorem 5, $\rho' = \frac{1}{\text{tr}(\rho M)} M\rho M$ where M is a projection. Basic linear algebra allows us to prove it using that M is a projection.
- $s = \text{Reset } q$. Rule [EVAL-RESET-OPT] yields $\rho' = p_0 \rho_0 + p_1 \text{gate}(\rho_1, X)$ where p_0 and p_1 correspond to measurement outcomes of q being 0 and 1, respectively, and X representing a unitary operator. By proving that probabilities are non-negative and their sum is unity, and that positive semi-definiteness and self-adjointness are preserved under convex combinations, ρ' retains the required properties.

Finally, the application of [EVAL-UNIFY] preserves the three properties of density matrices. If $\rho' = \frac{P_0}{P_0+P_1} \rho_1 + \frac{P_1}{P_0+P_1} \rho_2$, which is a convex combination of ρ_1 and ρ_2 , all properties are preserved, analogous to the $s = \text{Reset } q$ case. □

References

- [1] Wolfgang Scherer. *Mathematics of Quantum Computing*. Physics and Astronomy. Springer Cham, 1 edition, 2019.